

Exploring Understandability Factors in Business Process Models

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Summary of mitigations for threats to validity

This document complements the main article, providing detailed information on the threats mitigated through the study design. However, they have not been mentioned in the main article due to space limitations.

Conclusion validity		Construct validity	
Low statistical power	The sample size is according to the factors (5 samples per each factor, for 35 factors, a minimum of 175 samples) [1]	Inadequate preoperational explication of constructs	Variables based on understandability quality framework
Violated assumption of statistical tests	Checked in PCA/PCR analyses	Mono-operation bias	Subjects assessed multiple models
Fishing and the error rate	Not looking for causal effects but to explore relationships	Mono-method bias	Two different measures (understandability score and completion time)
Reliability of measures	Instruments were peer assessed and tested in pilot study	Confounding constructs and levels of constructs	We based the dependent and independent variables on previous experiments and quality frameworks
Reliability of treatment implementation	Implementation guided by the web app.	Interaction of different treatments	Single treatment
Random irrelevancies in experimental setting	No interruptions were observed during the activity	Interaction of testing and treatment	Subjects were not qualified according to their performance
Random heterogeneity of subjects	Considered and studied as personal factors.	Restricted generalizability across constructs	Two different measures (understandability score and completion time)
		Hypothesis guessing	Subjects were not aware of the hypothesis.
		Evaluation apprehension	Subjects were not qualified according to their performance
		Experimenter expectancies	Since it is an exploratory study, the research group had no previous expectancies on the relationships among variables.

Internal validity		External validity	
History	All the data was collected in the same activity, the same day	Interaction of selection and treatment	The selection does not represent all the population of business process model readers, but novice bpmn users with different levels of modelling experience among other personal factors.
Maturation	Maturation is a threat since we presented all the models in the same order.	Interaction of history and treatment	The activity was performed in a regular day and setting
Testing	Subjects participated just one time	Interaction of setting and treatment	Communication analysis models must not be representative of business process models with other notations (BPMN). We aim to extend the study to other notations.
Instrumentation	Since the web did not allow us to shuffle the models among participants, this could contribute to the maturation effect.	Interaction of different treatments	The study has a single treatment
Statistical regression	Subjects were not classified in groups		
Selection	The selection does not represent all the population of business process model readers, but novice bpmn users with different levels of modelling experience among other personal factors.		
Mortality	The subjects who dropped out did not have any particular characteristics in common		
Ambiguity about direction of causal influence	Causal influence is not under study.		